

POLICY ON HOUSING AND SETTLEMENT INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT FOR EARTHQUAKE-AFFECTED COMMUNITIES IN CIANJUR REGENCY

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Abstract

Studies on housing and settlements have been widely conducted in various countries, with varying focuses. This research uses a policy perspective with a research focus on the Study of Permanent Housing Development for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency. A magnitude 5.2 earthquake shook the Cianjur region on Monday, November 21, 2022. The Cianjur earthquake caused hundreds of casualties, people's homes were destroyed, and not a few roads were cracked because they were not strong enough to withstand the shock. The Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) revealed that the earthquake originated from the movement of the Cugenang fault. Reporting from the Instagram account of the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) of Cianjur Regency, as many as 593 people were seriously injured and 114,683 residents were forced to evacuate. As for other damage data, BPBD recorded 16 sub-districts consisting of 169 affected villages. Housing and Settlement Infrastructure Development Policy for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency includes using post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction activities as a means to build communities and stimulate the social and economic life of the community with the principles of sustainable development and disaster risk reduction. In residential relocation, environmental infrastructure and public and social facilities are still needed.

Keywords: Policy, Settlement, Earthquake, Cianjur.

INTRODUCTION

Studies on housing and settlements have been carried out in various countries, with various focuses, ranging from studies on slums (Akbar & Alfian, 2018; Paul Jones, 2016; Wijaya, 2016; Nursyahbani & Pigawati, 2015; Fitria & Setiawan, 2014), Uninhabitable Houses (Christiawan, 2019; Mevisitati, 2018), sustainable housing (Abu Hasan Abu Bakar, et al (2010); Pullen, S et al. (2010); Charles L Choughil (2007); Nessa Winston and Montserrat PE (2007); Aneke V. Hal (1998)) to about policies, including housing and settlement provision policies (Noveria, 2010), policy implementation (Adikara, 2016; Roebyantho, 2015).

The various studies above show that the problem of housing and residential areas can no longer be called a simple problem. Research on housing and residential areas, indeed, has been widely studied. However, this study uses a policy perspective with a research focus on the Study of Permanent Housing Development for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency and considers the importance of partnerships and networking between various stakeholders in the implementation of public affairs (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2007; Robinson, 2015).

The era of decentralization changed the order and governance of development in Indonesia. The issuance of Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Government which was later revised into Law Number 32 of 2004 and Law Number 23 of 2014, was a milestone in changing development management from centralized to decentralized. This change in management pattern provides greater space for local governments to manage urban areas according to the needs and character of each region. The momentum of decentralization provides space for several cities to innovate new creative programs so as to play a positive role in handling problems in urban residential areas.

In terms of functionality, housing and residential areas cannot be separated because housing as explained by Law No. 1 of 2011 is "A collection of houses as part of settlements, both urban and rural equipped with infrastructure, facilities and public utilities as an effort to fulfill a habitable house. While residential areas are intended as "Part of the living environment outside the protected area, both in the form of urban and rural areas that function as residential environments or residential environments.

Housing and settlement infrastructure development policy covers several main activities ranging from development planning, utilization and control, including institutional development, funding and financing systems as well as coordinated and integrated community roles (Article 1 paragraph 6 of Law No.1 of 2011). In terms of housing development policies and residential areas, the main problem that is often faced is how the government's role is in terms of providing land and other facilities and infrastructure.

A magnitude 5.2 earthquake shook the Cianjur region on Monday, November 21, 2022. The Cianjur earthquake caused hundreds of casualties, people's homes were destroyed, and not a few roads were cracked because they were not strong enough to withstand the shock. The Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) revealed that the earthquake originated from the movement of the Cugenang fault. Reporting from the Instagram account of the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) of Cianjur Regency, as many as 593 people were seriously injured and 114,683 residents were forced to evacuate. As for other damage data, BPBD recorded 16 sub-districts consisting of 169 affected villages.

The Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) through the Directorate General (Ditjen) of Housing targets permanent housing or relocation for people affected by the Cianjur earthquake to be completed. Currently, 95 units of Risha (Rumah Instan TSimple Sehat) have been completed in Sirnagalih Village, Cilaku District, Cianjur Regency, and the second location in Mulyasari Village, Mande District, Cianjur Regency.

Risha is a form of knock down technology used in healthy simple residential buildings, and is in accordance with Kimpraswil Decree No. 403 / KPTS / M / 2003 concerning Technical Guidelines for Healthy Simple Houses. Risha's technology that uses reinforced concrete materials and does not consume much material from nature is very feasible to be developed because it is environmentally friendly and meets standards. The advantages of Risha technology include: simple, fast, flexible, environmentally friendly, strong and durable and quality (Sabaruddin & Sukmana, 2015).

In addition to building earthquake-resistant houses with the Risha method, the Ministry of PUPR also completes Infrastructure, Facilities and Public Utilities (PSU) in the form of electricity connections, clean water channels and sanitation. Thus, the community can immediately inhabit the house and not stay too long in the refuge. The government through the Ministry of PUPR together with the Cianjur Regency Government has prepared a relocation area in Cilaku District covering an area of 2.5 hectares and in Mande District covering an area of 1.9 hectares for people whose homes are on the Cugenang active fault. Meanwhile, for people whose homes are not broken by the active Cugenang fault, there is no need to move to the relocation area. Because the government will continue to provide home repair assistance whose amount adjusts to the level of damage.

The purpose of this study is to analyze How Housing and Settlement Infrastructure Development Policies for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency. So that in the future it can be used as a reference in handling the construction of houses and settlements after the earthquake in other locations.

DISCUSSION

Cianjur Regency is located in West Java Province which is divided into 32 districts with an area of about 361,435 Ha. The northern administrative boundary is bordered by Bogor Regency and Purwakarta Regency; to the east it is bordered by Purwakarta Regency, Bandung Regency, West Bandung Regency, and Garut Regency; to the south it borders the Indian Ocean; to the west it is bordered by Sukabumi Regency and Bogor Regency.

The area affected by the earthquake covers 182 villages in 16 districts as follows: Cianjur, Karang Tengah, Warungkondang, Cilaku, Gekbrong, Cugenang, Cibeber, Sukaluyu, Sukaresmi, Pacet, Bojongpicung, Cikalong Kulon, Mande, Cipanas, Haurwangi, and Ciranjang. Based on infographic data from BPBD Cianjur Regency, on December 7, 2022, the earthquake had resulted in 334 deaths, 8 people in search, 593 people seriously injured and 44 people slightly injured. The earthquake also displaced 114,683 people.

Housing and Settlement Infrastructure Development Policies for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency include: Using post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction activities as a means to build communities and stimulate the social and economic life of the community with the principles of sustainable development and disaster risk reduction; Implemented with a good governance approach, through effective coordination between activity implementers, and prioritizing the aspirations of disaster victims; Especially for recovery activities in the field of housing and community life, carried out with a participatory approach in accordance with local cultural characteristics, while increasing community understanding of disaster risk reduction; Carried out by taking into account the technical standards of healthy and decent houses and settlement improvements with the principle of *build back better and safer*; Implemented by prioritizing the welfare of all parties through the provision of accurate information as well as technical and licensing services, including the provision of a community complaint unit; Implemented with accountable, efficient, effective, and accountable fund disbursement and accountability mechanisms in accordance with

applicable laws and regulations; Implemented by local governments in accordance with their authority, through effective coordination and cooperation and between cross-sectoral parties with monitoring and control mechanisms in accordance with applicable laws and regulations; Taking into account the impact of damage and budget availability, the post-bencana rehabilitation and reconstruction plan will be implemented in stages over 36 months.

The Housing and Settlement Sector Strategy includes: Initial data collection of house damage is collected by BPBD based on reports from affected sub-districts, sourced from RT, RW to villages. The data is then verified by the verification team by involving technical SKPD; the results of house verification (*by name by address*) are determined through a Decree (SK) of the regent. In order to ensure participation, transparency and accountability, public testing and socialization to affected communities are carried out by validating the level of damage to houses in accordance with home ownership data and receiving assistance. If there is a correction, a revision is made as stated in the regent's decree. During the emergency response period, the West Java Provincial government has allocated a budget through financial assistance for the construction of temporary residential houses as a handling priority. During the recovery transition period, the government has allocated a budget through the Ready-to-Use Fund (DSP) to the National Disaster Management Agency for Shelter Waiting Fund (DTH) and the creation of residential houses remains as a handling priority. In accordance with the president's directive for permanent housing for heavy, medium and light damaged houses, stimulant assistance will be provided through BNPB DSP grants. In residential relocation, environmental infrastructure and public and social facilities are still needed.

The Infrastructure Sector Strategy is carried out by rehabilitating and reconstructing the infrastructure sector in order to support the implementation of the community's economic recovery; Rebuilding public infrastructure by taking into account related sector policies and district spatial plans; Restoring functions and rebuilding public infrastructure, namely transportation, and water resources; Rehabilitation and reconstruction of infrastructure refers to related technical standards; Submit a request for proposals for post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction of the infrastructure sector to BNPB through RR grants in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

Post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction activities are the responsibility of the government affected by the disaster (PP No. 21 of 2008 concerning the Implementation of Disaster Management). Post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction are coordinated at the local level by BPBD Cianjur Regency and by BNPB for coordination at the central level. Substantial technical implementation is carried out by ministries/agencies and/or regional apparatus work units (SKPD) in provinces and / or districts. International institutions, non-government foreign institutions and/or non-government institutions involved in post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction must coordinate with BNPB and BPBD together with ministries/agencies and SKPD.

After the implementation of the post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction action plan is carried out, it is necessary to develop a policy strategy linked to the regular planning and budgeting cycle to ensure the continuity of post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction in "normal" development according to the authority of the relevant agencies.

In accordance with the mandate of Law Number 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management, local governments also need to strive to implement: Disaster management planning through the introduction and assessment of disaster threats, conducting disaster risk analysis studies, conducting vulnerability analysis and capacity of regions and communities in disaster management, identifying disaster risk reduction actions, and preparing Disaster Management Plan (RPB) and Regional Action Plan documents Disaster Risk Reduction (RAD PRB);

Reducing the factors that cause disaster risk through control and implementation of spatial planning by reviewing spatial and regional planning based on disaster mitigation, mainstreaming disaster risk reduction in RPJMD, RKPD, RKA and DPA SKPD, and RTRW; With the earthquake disaster in Cianjur Regency, it is expected that the local government will conduct a review of the RTRW of the affected districts; Research, education, and training on disaster management and preparedness through the implementation of disaster risk reduction education into formal and informal education systems and the provision of counseling and training to communities in disaster-prone areas; Based on disaster potential, prevention, and disaster risk reduction, controlling the use of space and area through licensing mechanisms and technical development requirements according to the authority of the relevant institution; Allocate an adequate disaster management budget from the APBD.

CONCLUSION

Housing and Settlement Infrastructure Development Policies for Earthquake-Affected Communities in Cianjur Regency include: Using post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction activities; Implemented with a good governance approach; Carried out by taking into account the technical standards of healthy and decent houses and settlement improvements with the principle of *build back better and safer*.

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